

A Qualitative Study on the Social Impact of Industrialisation in Badli

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Abstract: *The article aims to investigate and analyze the social impact of industrialization on Badli. Badli is one of the largest industrial zones in Delhi which also bears large slums neighboring to the industries. The literature available on the area is also limited to news articles and government reports, thus further research on Badli is required. The social implications were examined through naturalistic observational research and unstructured interviews of 10 individuals from Badli. Using thematic analysis and secondary data analysis the data was interpreted into common themes and key ideas. The analysis showed most Industries in Badli are unauthorized and have issues such as unemployment, child labor, hazardous working conditions, nominal wages, producing illegal substances and lack of healthcare management. People living in the neighboring slum areas suffer from issues such as poor health care facilities, below par educational infrastructure, high crime rates, harmful drainage and ventilation services, congested housing structures, economic disparity, and toxic family environment. Thus Industrialization has deeper implications on the society of Badli which can be attributed to the influx of migrants, industries and poor governance by the administrative authorities to control and manage the industrial process in Badli. It can be concluded that there is a huge correlation between social change and industrialization. Further studies are required to create socio-economic policies catering to the situation in Badli for a long-lasting sustainable effect on the area.*

Key Words: *Society, Social, Social Change, Industrialization, Slums.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Badli is one of the oldest villages in Delhi which is located in the North-west district of Delhi. Badli is surrounded by state borders from North-West Delhi and North-East Delhi. Spanning over 936.4 hectares of area and demographically situated on the right side of the western Yamuna canal. The canal works as a demarcation between the neighboring district of Praladhpur and Badli. Historically Badli functioned as a camp for early invaders of Delhi. It was also a place that was famous for its flush crops. Not much history can be found about Badli in literature, except the only evidence being news articles and area reports. Before the land acquisition, it was mostly occupied by farmer communities, mainly the Ahirs (North Indian Tribe). The roots of the industrialization process in Badli could be traced back from 1964 when for the first time roughly 6.5 acres of land was acquired for the creation of a transport station. But large scale acquisition was only done in the period from 1981-82. Sooner Badli completely turned into an industrial area and with the advent of industries developed the need for workers, which was facilitated by the on-going surge of migrations from other states to Delhi. This coupled with the influx of liberation policies lead to Badli becoming an area with a 71% Industrial concentration, as of 2018, with little to no room left to build safe residential areas away from the pre-built slums. Industries are now the major source for income for the inhabitants except for some farming done on the outskirts of Badli. The quality of life in the area is abysmal and most of the residents are from lower-income, working-class backgrounds. The subsequent aim of this research is to qualitatively look at the Social impact of Industrialization on Badli and also give an overview of the contemporary situation in Badli.

2.Literature Review:

Unfortunately, even after about two decades of planning, there are very few detailed studies on the social and cultural responses of the agrarian population to the rapidly developing industrial complexes in modern India. The literature on the sociology of industrialization is largely based on the unique experience of western society. Some of the typical characteristics of modern Western society are conceived as particularly adaptive to the requirements of industrialization (Gupta & Das,1973, p. 02-04). The impact of industry varies from society to society since this process normally happens to correspond with the socio-cultural matrix of the particular society. It is not necessary, therefore that the same significant consequences of industrialization experienced by one society should attend to another industrializing society. As it is socio-economic changes in the context of industrialization does not imply that there was no change at all before industrialization. But the process of industrialization finds that there is a consistent pattern of socioeconomic change (Dhanikachalam, 1988, p. 214-215).

2.1. Indian Studies on the impact of industrialization:

Vaid, K.N.(1963-64) studied the influence of industrial work on workers of a factory in Kota in Rajasthan. He found that the factory system initiates changes in the attitudes and values of its workforce. The industrial experience increases expectations and aspirations and the worker wants good wages, housing facilities job security and opportunities for advancement. His study indicates that basic security against unemployment, illness, and incapacity was provided by the joint family. He concludes that industrialization influences social structure value system, motivations and norms and in turn is also influenced by them (Vaid,1969; Dhanikachalam,1988). Sheth, N.R.(1968) made a sociological study of workers in a factory named "oriental" at the District place of Rajnagar in Gujarat state; from July 1956 to July 1958. He asserts that "it is considered traditional institutions are a hindrance in the way of economic growth", but the study of oriental shows that it is not so in all cases. So the values of a pre-industrial society seem to co-exist with those of industrial society, producing an intermixture of traditionalistic and rationalistic norms" (Sheth,1971; Dhanikachalam,1988). A study of rural emigration by A.B. Parameswarappa, Devangare examines the impact of industrialization on the village community and rural exodus in Maggadhalli, a small village of Dharwar district in Karnataka. The study reveals that industrialization has dismantled several traditional occupations in rural India and created footloose processes for a large number of occupational groups. Industrialization and migration have an inward relationship. Rural-urban migration distributes the population in two communities and leads to rapid urbanization and family change. The old migrants have been the source for new migrants. They are a source of social change in Maggadhalli (Dhanikachalam, 1988, p. 64-65). Further, in a different study, it was observed that children of the industrial workers, born and brought up in the industrial town, are more prone to the urban way of life and there are a tendency to take up urban – industrial occupations (Gupta & Das, 1973, p. 219-2020). In a recent study done in the rural Marathwada region in Maharashtra showed how Urban Industrialization impacted the region. People have many problems such as- Over-population, Health, No clean water supply, Electricity, Education, Jobs, Roads, Lack of security, Illiterate administration, etc. 79 percent of rural households do not have access to credit facilities. Due to poor sanitation and lack of toilets, the people are facing hygiene-related and illness problems. Most of the schools in villages don't have proper classrooms, teaching equipment, playgrounds and even basic facilities like clean toilets (Baburao,2016, p. 268-275). Balogh (1966), studied the impacts of industries on employment in developing countries revealed that more than 70% of the working population is employed in the agricultural sector and not the industrial sector. Also, industries don't always create employment for rural people as some industries require entrepreneurial and managerial talent which lacks amongst the rural people (Muhammad & Yew, 2018, p. 27-28). It is also empirically proven that the higher the length of service of workers higher the chances of health problems. Those workers employed to prolong the period in factories commonly suffer from breathing trouble, cough. Asthma, fever, skin allergies and chest pain. (Dhanikachalam, 1988, p. 203-204).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

3.1 Primary Study:

The Primary study comprised of personal interviews of 10 individuals from Badli:- 5 residents of the slums, 4 workers from Badli industries and 1 social worker from a local NGO chapter named 'Pahal'. The interviews were conducted by the first author who was a social work intern stationed in Badli. The interviewees were selected through the database of an NGO named 'Pahal' operating in Badli. Interviews were conducted in different settings as the workers were interviewed outside their factories, slum dwellers were interviewed in their houses and the social worker was interviewed at their office. The interviews followed an unstructured approach, such interviews tend to be more like an everyday conversation that is informal, open-ended and flexible (Trueman,2015). Questions used to elicit responses from the interviewees varied according to the individuals as workers were asked questions related to industries, slum dwellers were asked questions to elicit responses on life and history of Badli and the social worker was asked questions to elicit a socio-economic overview on Badli.

3.2 Secondary Study:

The secondary study used Observational Research applied in both the industrial and residential areas of Badli. The areas were observed in their naturalist state and were simultaneously transcribed in an observation report. Observational research was used to systematically observe and record the area to obtain specific characteristics of the individuals and the area. Within an observation, a naturalistic setting involves observing people's behavior in the environment in which it typically occurs (Price et al, 2017, p. 00-01). The observational study was done over a span of one month by daily observations.

3.3 Analysis

Both Primary and Secondary Study data was compiled and analyzed using Thematic Analysis to create compatible and common themes, patterns and structures present in both the studies. Thematic analysis is a generic approach to data analysis that enables data sources to be analyzed in terms of the principal concepts or themes (Silva, 2017, p. 00-01). The themes were developed to enable the data to be reduced to key ideas. The coding and theme

development followed an inductive way; which was directed by the data that was retrieved from interviews and observation reports. Simultaneously, Secondary Data Analysis was also utilized to also bring up prior literature and factual information in perspective to the themes generated. Secondary data analysis involves the use of information that someone else has gathered (Foley, 2019, p. 01). Secondary data analysis was conducted on Delhi government reports, land acquisition records and news articles. The following approach to analysis allows optimal and seamless integration of data from both the studies, including knowledge of prior literature, into an easy to understand themes and patterns that covered all the aspects from both the studies.

4.RESULTS:

4.1 History of Industrialization:

Most of the contemporary industries in Badli were established in the 1990s when the ‘New Economic Policy’ was implemented by the government, which brought in the privatization of the industrial sector but the history of Industrialization dates back to the early days of Delhi (Sengupta, 2017). The land acquisition process was mostly done by using the state government under the headline of modernization and urbanization. Lured by the availability of skilled personnel, the prospects of obtaining access to the corridors of power in Delhi and the once-pleasant environment, businessmen have been flocking here from the '50s and '60s (Thakurta, 2013, p. 01). The initial policy to kickstart these policies was the ‘Master Plan Of Delhi’ 1962 under which large sums of land were acquired by the government from the native farmers of Badli, followed by the land acquired for building the Transport station in 1964. The compensation amount that farmers got in return for these land acquisitions were nominal. One major malpractice committed by the government was to allow the Delhi Development Authority’s (DDA) inaction against the unauthorized settling of migrants near the industries and factories. The major reason for the inaction was the industry owners paying large sums of money to allow the migrants to settle in close proximity to the industries. This allowed industry owners to fulfill their requirements for cheap and easily accessible labor. The slums or the unauthorized residential areas were also created because settling in these areas was cheap and houses were close to the industrial workplaces. This started the surge of building houses and then further expanding them leading to areas becoming narrower, congested and overpopulated. The Centre caved in to pressure the state government of Delhi to further industrialize the state. Indeed, the pressure to industrialize Greater Delhi has been enormous. Despite official restrictions, the factory population in the Union territory alone has doubled over the last 12 years, with roughly 4,000 new ones being tagged on "provisionally" every year. In the decade between 1960 and 1970, the number of industrial units multiplied by 600 percent, before slowing down under the pressures of urbanization (Thakurta, 2013, p. 02). The employment pattern was also affected as this acquisition strip away the main occupation of the farmers i.e. ‘Agriculture’, this brought 78% of the farmers changing their profession and further leading to an increment of over 1500% in the employment rates in industries and factories.

4.2 Present State of Industries:

Post-Industrialization, Badli changed a lot by becoming a very accessible industrial area with the creation of Samaypur Badli Metro Station and also due to the rise of many public transport facilities such as ‘E-rickshaws’ (Battery-run Rickshaws) and ‘Gramin-Sewa’ (a modified Tata SUV Vehicle) which further made the transportation cheap and accessible. The Badli is now entirely dominated by industries and consequently, most of the workers reside in the surrounding slums build throughout the industrial phase of Badli. The majority of the industries are manufacturing-focused plants mainly comprising of plastic, electrical components, farming equipment, packaging, and cable industries. Most industries and factories are unregistered, with only a fraction of them being registered and authorized within the Delhi government legal industrial framework. For state governments, these industries are a civic threat because they are illegally operating in unauthorized areas of Badli, which are not suitable and authorized for an industrial setup. They also perform illicit activities such as tax evasion, child labor, production of illegal substances and hazardous working conditions. For workers, these industries provide employment opportunities but also bring serious life issues such as healthcare, abysmal job security and lesser pay than government standards. The ‘Delhi State Industrial and Infrastructure Development Corporation’ (DSIIDC) recently brought down an initiative to cease more than 51,000 illegal industries in Delhi, this has caused massive unemployment in the Badli area. The DSIIDC claims that the main reason for ceasing is the rising pollution level in Delhi, as in 2018 Delhi hit an all-time high in unhealthy air quality index. The reason for pollution was placed on the industries in Badli as they are dumping huge amounts of industrial wastes and emitting toxic fumes (Singh, Manohar, 2018). As a consequence of this ceasing “More than 5000 industrial workers have lost their jobs after the government ceasing industries”, told by a worker during a protest against low wages and unemployment in Badli. One of the key problems for these workers is also low wages and salary as they are being paid Rs.6,000 for 12 hours of labor as per told by the interviewed workers. According to the minimum wage act of 1948- “an adult cannot be working for more than 9 hours in factories” and also they should be paid Rs.14,000/pm which is the Delhi government set standard. The unemployment caused by the government industrial ceiling has also caused many workers to turn into businessmen and when such businesses are open by them,

they are being troubled by Police in forms of weekly debt collections, as told by the interviewed workers. The workers who don't opt for a business occupation get into illicit criminal or illegal activities to earn a living. The healthcare facilities in industries are borderline substandard as most industries are not following the healthcare and medical norms set for the workers. When it was asked by a worker that- 'What medical norms are followed in most industries in Badli?' he said: "There are no medical norms in factories, the least I remember was a medical check-up done at the joining day, many years back, like 7-10 or even 12 years back". A hospital for workers has been opened but it suffers from the problem of proximity, as the hospital is very distant from most of the industries in Badli.

4.3 Life in Slums:

The conditions in the neighboring slums are much worse than in industries, attributed to the overall structure of Badli. The area of Badli is bifurcated into 2 areas: Industries and Slums. Industries being the first to built then slums developing around them. Within the residential areas of slums, there is segregation where those people who were able to earn a good living build better fully built houses slightly away from the slums. Drainage and sewage are a source of constant issues in the slums, as drain lines run in between houses causing major sanitation problems as people get in direct contact with the sewage water. Due to this, respiratory diseases are common in slums and many lives have been lost due to such diseases. Most of the houses are cramped half-built houses, housing a family of 6-7 on average. The inhabitants of these areas are mainly migrants from Uttar Pradesh and Bihar who live in these houses for shorter periods ranging from 1-2 years. As for these migrants, this period is for the initial settlement to check if it is feasible to settle in Delhi. This mode of temporary settlement affects the condition of houses, as most houses are left in poor conditions due to the settler's shorter stay. Most houses follow the same pattern of double-storeyed construction with an attached stairway. This construction pattern allows households to run various in-house business where the bottom floor is used as a shop and the 2nd floor as the living area. The streets often get littered with drainage waste and if there is rain then all the drainage choked in the drainage lines gets collected on the road and at times drainage water even reaches the height of up to 4 feet. The electric poles in the area are left loose turning into huge clusters, due to which many people have lost their lives by mistakingly walking on these loose electric wires lying on the roads. The abysmal infrastructure can further be explained by a case where a woman was killed and two others injured when a portion of a three-story building collapsed in the Jeevan Park area of Badli (TNN,2019). There is a strong sense of community among the people of Badli. "Internal conflicts don't happen in the area, due to the common background of the settlers coming from a common state and also a sense of unity has been established in the society", as stated by an interviewed social worker. Most of the services such as grocery shops, repairing services, fruits and vegetable vendors are self-sustained by the community. The family demographics of the area comprise most households having 4-5 children. This deeply affects the sustainability and overall quality of life in slums as these households have more children to provide quality life than their low-medium income can sustain. Healthcare in the residential areas of Badli is an inaccessible facility. As there is no hospital in the entire district of Badli and the residents have to go to Ambedkar Hospital in Rohini Sector 18, which is very far away from Badli. Many people have lost their lives due to the unavailability of hospitals. Polio is a huge health issue in Badli and many children have been a victim to the same. The only facilitation in healthcare came from the opening up of local medical dispensaries, which offers medicines to the residents. Also a prominent local doctor named Dr. Surendra Chandra charges only RS.10 for a medical checkup and treatment.

4.4 Education and Children:

When the initial phase of industrial and community settlement was taking place education took a major setback in the area. It was through government and allied NGOs support that the condition of education improved as the comparative enrolment rates of children from the last decade show considerable improvement. Child labor is still a major issue that requires a solution as it has led to several children dropping out of schools. The reason for mass dropout rates is the incapacity of Badli residents to sustain an entire family on the incomes earn from daily wages, thus children are put to work to ensure a steady income. Most children roam around bare-footed and wear tattered clothes. The lack of schools is a major issue, as there are only 2 privately run schools in the entire area. The conditions in the 2 private schools are not optimal due to over enrolment of 100 students in one class. Recently built 10 'Anganwadis' (Rural Child Welfare Centre) are the only institutions for elementary and primary education in Badli. The only viable schools are in other areas distant from Badli making them an unfeasible option for children. In a lot of cases, children have dropped out of school due to long-distance traveling. The primary struggle for children mainly stems from their toxic family environment, as these children witness acts such as Domestic violence, Substance abuse, criminal activities. As in a tale of extreme parental cruelty, an alcoholic father flung to death his two-year-old ailing son into a Delhi canal, just three days after he abandoned his two starving and ill daughters in their house (Indo-Asian News Service, 2016). In another case, an 18-year-old boy allegedly committed suicide, a day after his sister was allegedly molested by a group of men in the Badli area (Press Trust of India, 2017). Such acts deeply affect the mental health of a child, as most of these children grow up with these traumatic events and some even get into criminal activities or substance abuse due to lack of parenting and toxic family environment.

4.5 Crimes in Badli

The crime rates in Badli is one of the highest in the entire state of Delhi. Various news articles have even stated Badli as the badlands of the Delhi due to it being the center of the crimes occurring in Delhi. Times of India in its article on “Crimes in Delhi” stated North-East Delhi accounting to 70% of crimes in Delhi (TNN, 2016). One person was killed and another critically injured when two motorcycle-borne assailants shot at them from close range in the Badli area (Indo-Asian News Service, 2015). It is often stated that slums are the common cause for most of the crimes in the area that are committed by slum dwellers or workers. Due to economic pressure and unemployment. “People don’t go out after its dark in Badli, as it is very prominent to be attacked by someone in the narrow and dimly lit lanes that are choked with garbage”, told by an interviewed resident of Badli. As evident by the kidnapping incident that happened in 2014 where a 14-year-old girl was kidnapped when she came out of her house to buy something from across the street. In another case, A nine-year-old girl was raped on Saturday allegedly by a man who took her to his shanty in a nearby area in Badli (Press Trust of India, 2018). In January 2018 more than 40 children were rescued from the factories, who were trafficked to work in the factories from different parts of the country, predominately Madhya Pradesh (Mohan, 2018). Alcohol is one of the biggest reasons for crime in Badli, as it not only leads to domestic violence but even deadly altercations between individuals. A man was allegedly shot dead by his friend while they were drinking in Badli (Press Trust of India, 2018). State government and Delhi Police have taken contemporary measures to decrease crime rates in the area such as CCTV cameras, bringing the area into the Zonal Integrated Police Network (ZIPNET) and increasing police presence in both industrial and residential areas.

5. CONCLUSION:

As the research has demonstrated during the early industrialization phase of Delhi that started from the late 1960s led to large scale agricultural land acquisition in Badli. Soon several industries and businesses started setting up in Badli. At the same time, Delhi saw a huge influx of migrants from other states who required work and a place to live. Settling near the industries became a viable option for them as it ensured employment in the industries and houses close to their workplaces. The state government and land authorities also allowed the settlement of migrants where large settlements were built in very small spaces thus creating congested and overpopulated slums. Analysis and interpretation of both the survey and interview data showed that most industries in Badli are unregistered and are responsible for a lot of issues in Badli such as unemployment, workplace casualties, hazardous working conditions, low wage of workers, illegal substance production, increased pollution levels, and child labor. Industrialization had deeper implications on life in the residential areas where most of the workers lived. The condition of slums is abysmal with no proper drainage and ventilation services leading to various diseases i.e. coupled with there being no hospitals in the entire area. There are only 2 schools in the entire area and the enrollment rates of children are not increasing due to child labor and lack of schools. The area poses one of the highest crime rates in Delhi as most of the slum dwellers and workers alike get into criminal activities due to loss of jobs, unemployment, economic pressure and children getting exposed to the crime wave. Over 4 decades of Industrialization had lasting social effects on Badli and thus it can be stated there is a huge correlation between social change and industrialization. Due to the small sample scale of the study with qualitative interviews and observational research, it becomes imminent for researchers and authorities to further explore and research the area using quantitative research to improvise large scale Socio-Economic policies in Badli.

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